

Constant Voltage and Constant Current Charging Wireless Power Transfer System a Simple to Operate and Flexible Approach

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Abstract: A constant voltage (CV) and constant current (CC) charging stage are common components of an electric vehicle's (EV) Li-ion battery charging profile. For CC and CV outputs in an EV wireless charging system, this letter presents an easily understood and adjustable architecture. Series-series topology for the CC output and inductor-capacitor-capacitor-series topology for the CV output are the two possible configurations for this proposed solution. In contrast to conventional techniques that use many passive components and relays for reconfiguration, only one relay is introduced in this topology. In addition, shifting the CC and CV does not need frequency variation. Simulation is done using MATLAB/Simulink model. Key words: Li-ion battery, Transmitter, Receiver, Constant voltage (CV) charging, constant current (CC), inductor-capacitor-capacitor-series (LCC-S), reconfigurable, series-series (SS), wireless power transfer (WPT).

INTRODUCTION

A greater level of user satisfaction than conventional plug-in chargers is offered by wireless power transfer (WPT), which enables autonomous charging of electric vehicles (EVs) without the need for human involvement. Due to the fact that batteries are charged via cables at charging stations, batteries

used as energy storage units require more time to charge than vehicles that run primarily on gasoline.

However, it is thought to be difficult to plug-in charge electric vehicles (EVs) in windy, wet or snowy conditions. For a simple charging alternative, it is thus advised to convert to WPT. The driver can place the electric vehicle above the static coil while the battery is being charged thanks to a WPT technology. WPT is a simpler way to charge the battery in an electric vehicle (EV) without requiring wire connections.

As EVs could decrease carbon emissions when gasoline-powered automobiles are replaced, the market for electric vehicles (EVs) is expanding quickly. One of the most important technical problems with EVs is charging. Due to its many benefits, including automation, safety, ease of use and lack of human labour, wireless charging for electric vehicles (EVs) attracts a lot of interest and is now a hot topic in study.

Owing to their great power density, Li-ion batteries are frequently seen in EVs. Constant current (CC) and constant voltage (CV) charging are common charging profiles for Li-ion batteries. The wireless charging device must thus have both a CC and a CV output in order to meet these criteria. CC and CV outputs can be obtained in a number of methods, according to recent literature. To create CC and CV

outputs at various working frequencies, the first way involves switching the working frequencies.

Zero phase angle, power, cannot be ensured at these two frequency locations, though. Furthermore, as per J2954 from the Society of Automotive Engineers, reaching an objective within a restricted operating frequency which means between 79 and 90 kHz is not a simple task. An alternative approach involves transitioning between different topologies to take into account CC and CV charging, such switching from the series-series (S-S) topology to the inductor-capacitor-capacitor-series (LCC-S) topology.

The current version of this technology involves the addition of several passive components, such as inductors and capacitors or the use of numerous relays to reconfigure the arrangement of components. In order to provide CC and CV outputs without adding more passive components, a unique topology is proposed in this letter. The S-S topology is formed by utilizing the three resonant loops from the LCC-S topology. There is just one relay in use. This provides a straightforward and affordable option for CC and CV outputs.

PROPOSED TOPOLOGY FOR CC AND CV CHARGING

The Fig. 1 shows the proposed topology for the outputs of CC and CV. The relative self-inductance, series capacitance and current of the transmitter (receiver) are denoted as L_T (L_R), C_T (C_R) and I_T (I_R). Mutual inductance is known as M_{TR} . C_F is the parallel capacitance, while L_F is the compensatory inductance. That is L_F 's current or I_F . The inverters dc voltage is V_{INV} . Load resistance is denoted by R_L . The voltage and current used for charging are V_{REC} and I_{REC} correspondingly.

Fig. 1. Proposed topology for CC and CV outputs.

Three resonant loops comprise the proposed topology: Loop 1 can be made up of L_F and C_F , Loop 2 is formed up of C_F , C_T , and L_T , and Loop 3 is composed up of L_R and C_R . The resonant frequency ω_0 thus equals

$$\omega_0 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{L_F C_F}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{L_F \frac{C_F C_T}{C_F + C_T}}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{L_R C_R}} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 2. Proposed system for CC output. (a) Topology. (b) Equivalent circuit.

Fig. 3. Current flow paths at the CC mode. (a) With positive U1 and positive U2. (b) With positive U1 and negative U2. (c) With zero U1 and negative U2. (d) With zero U1 and positive U2.

Synchronous rectification is the manner in which the rectifier operates. Consequently, the ac voltage of the rectifier U2 and the equivalent ac load resistance REQ can be written as

$$\begin{cases} R_{EQ} = \frac{8}{\pi^2} R_L \\ U_2 = \frac{2\sqrt{2}}{\pi} V_{REC}. \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 4. Proposed system for CV output. (a) Topology. (b) Equivalent circuit.

Fig. 5. Current flow paths at the CV mode. (a) With positive U1 and positive U2. (b) With zero U1 and negative U2.

CC Output:

As seen in Fig. 2(a), the relay is turned off for the CC output, and a S-S topology powered by a half-bridge inverter is created. Fig. 2(b) depicts the analogous circuit for the CC output. The transmitter's (receiver's) equivalent resistance is represented by RT (RR). U1 is the inverter's equivalent AC voltage. Fig. 3 displays the current flow routes of the phase-shift between U1 and U2, which is regulated at 90° in the CC mode. U1 can be written as

$$U_1 = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{\pi} V_{INV} \quad (3)$$

CV Output:

Fig. 4(a) depicts the formation of an LCC-S topology powered by a half-bridge inverter for CV output, wherein the relay and switch S4 are continuously ON and the switch S3 is continuously OFF. Fig. 4(b) displays the same circuit for the CV output. The resistance that LF is equal to is called RF. In the CV mode, the phase shift between U1 and U2 is

regulated with the same phase, and Fig. 5 illustrates its current flow paths.

SIMULATION RESULTS

The early version is modeled and simulated using MATLAB/Simulink, and the initial values contains an overview of the parameters. The main waveforms for simulation voltage and current are shown in Fig. 6.

Fig.6. (a)

Fig.6. (b)

Fig. 6. Key simulation voltage and current waveforms. (a) CC output with $RL = 28 \Omega$. (b) CV output with $RL = 28 \Omega$.

CONCLUSION

In a wireless charging system, this letter proposed an effortless and adjustable architecture for the CC and CV outputs. By utilizing the three resonant loops, the LCC-S topology may be changed to the S-S topology. In contrast to the LCC-S architecture, the suggested solution just uses a relay and does not include any additional inductors or capacitors, unlike the current systems that make use of several passive components and relays. Additionally, the system complies with current regulations with ease because it operates at a single frequency. A functional model was created. The suggested systems efficacy was confirmed by the results of the study.

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